

FROM THEORY TO PRACTICE

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Abstract:

Academic IELTS (International English Language Testing System) is a world renowned international testing system for students who wish to enter and study abroad and at prestigious universities in our country. Studying and preparing for Academic IELTS requires a systematic approach, knowledge of assessment criteria and practice, and then students will be able to pass Academic IELTS successfully.

Keywords: Academic IELTS, Reading, Listening, Writing, Speaking, skill, practice, program, elective course.

For quite a long period of time, the last 3 decades, a large number of school graduates from our country have shown a desire to enter and study at the universities abroad, in the UK, the USA, Canada, Australia, New Zealand and in a number of European and Asian countries where there are educational programs in English. But a mandatory requirement for leaving and studying is passing the English language proficiency exam according to international standards Academic IELTS (International English Language Testing System) - a world-renowned international testing system developed to confirm the level of proficiency in English for those for whom it is not native.

Even universities in Kazakhstan, such as Nazarbayev University, Kazakh-British Technical University KBTU, KIMEP require mandatory passing of the IELTS exam with an average score of 6 and 7 for admission to a bachelor's degree.

The IELTS exam was created jointly by three organizations: the British Council, the Australian Educational Organization and the University of Cambridge.

IELTS certificates are valid in more than 125 countries around the world, almost all over Europe, in the UK, Australia, the USA, Canada, New Zealand.

The list of countries accepting IELTS includes: Argentina, Austria, Belgium, Bolivia, Brazil, Bulgaria, Chile, China, Colombia, Croatia, Cuba, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Dominican Republic, Ecuador, Egypt, Estonia, Fiji, Finland, France, Germany, India, Hungary, Israel, Italy, Jamaica, Japan, Latvia, Luxembourg, Nepal, Vietnam, Venezuela, Thailand, Switzerland, Singapore, Poland, Korea, Norway, Peru, Philippines, Slovakia.

It should be noted that General Training IELTS for work and immigration is the same in structure, but differs in the complexity of some parts from Academic IELTS. Students who are ready to take Academic IELTS can easily score high scores in General Training IELTS.

	IELTS Academic	IELTS General Training
Reading	More complex texts from scientific journals and textbooks	Texts from newspapers, advertisements, instructions, simpler in content
Listening	More complex texts from scientific journals and textbooks	A little simpler in content
Writing	Writing Task 1 – analysis and description of a graph/diagram/process/table Writing Task 2 – essay (more complex)	Task 1 – write a letter (formal/informal) Writing Task 2 – essay (simpler)
Speaking	The same for both	The same for both

For 12 years, the specialized boarding school-lyceum named after N. Nurmakov has included an elective course "Linguistic Stock" in the curriculum for grades 9-11 according to the author's educational and methodological program, 1 hour per week.

This educational and methodological program consists of 3 stages of study:

Grade 9 "Ready for FCE" (34 hours) by Roy Norris

Grade 10 "Ready for IELTS" (34 hours) by Sam McCarter

Grade 11 "Ready for IELTS" (34 hours) by Sam McCarter

Grade 9 is a preparatory stage for studying the Ready for IELTS (Academic IELTS) program, which is based on the Ready for First Certificate program.

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Academic IELTS covers testing of all the basic skills necessary for a person (the ability to speak, understand speech by ear, write and read). According to these skills, Academic IELTS consists of four parts:

- IELTS Listening
- IELTS Reading
- IELTS Writing
- IELTS Speaking

Students complete IELTS Listening and IELTS Reading tasks according to strictly proposed IELTS tasks, such as multiple choice, sentence completion, matching, labeling a map, plan, diagram, classification, True / False / Not Given questions; identification of writer's views/claims. Listening and reading with such tasks, students have difficulty adapting to the vocabulary and semantic content of the texts proposed for Academic IELTS for several months.

At the beginning of the study, students have difficulty with Writing Task 1, where they need to analyze data from different types of graphs, such as Line graph, Bar chart, Pie chart, compare table data, maps of the area, describe a process based on a picture with a time limit of 20 minutes to write 150 words. By practicing these types of data analysis and learning the necessary vocabulary, students show success over time. Writing task 2 requires a detailed, expanded answer with examples on the proposed topic in 250 words within 45 minutes. Students study the writing requirements and assessment criteria to get high scores.

Particular attention is paid to IELTS Speaking, which consists of 3 parts, Speaking Part 1, a dialogue containing personal questions. For example: What is your home town like? Are you good at Art? Do you usually celebrate your birthday? What is your daily routine? There are a huge number of such questions, the likelihood that the examiner will ask them when taking the IELTS exam is small. Students study the assessment criteria for getting a high score, watch videos of real exams with assessment for low and high scores, memorize connecting words, necessary phrases and learn to demonstrate complex and varied grammar in answers to questions. Speaking Part 2 is a 2-minute monologue speech on a given topic, when you are given the opportunity to prepare for 1 minute, take notes and use them when answering. This part also requires a lot of practice. Speaking Part 3 is questions on the topic of Speaking Part 2, but of a more global scale, affecting various areas of economics, politics and education.

Monitoring of the last three years shows an increasing growth dynamics in the number of students who passed Academic IELTS at N. Nurmakov school from 9 students in the 2022-2023 academic year with an average score of 6.0 - 7.5 to 19 students in the 2024-2025 academic year with an average score of 5.5 - 7.5. Studying the English language program in senior classes in the amount of 2 suggested hours per week, students face the difficulty of passing Academic IELTS. Therefore, the introduction of an additional elective course on studying Academic IELTS is a modern necessity for studying in senior classes, since our updated educational program in schools today is aimed at the development and formation of a competitive personality in the field of education and science in the world.

References:

- [1]. Sam McCarter. *Ready for IELTS coursebook.*-Macmillan Education, 2008.-282 p.
- [2]. Sam McCarter. *Ready for IELTS workbook.*- Macmillan Education, 2008.-152 p.
- [3]. Roy Norris. *Ready for FCE coursebook.*-Macmillan Education, 2008.-285 p.
- [4]. *Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated July 27, 2007 No. 319 - III "On Education" (with amendments and additions as of 05/18/2024) // Official website of the Parliament of the Republic of Kazakhstan. - 2007. - P. 1-50.*
- [5]. Pauline Cullen, Amanda French. *The Official Cambridge Guide To IELTS.*-Cambridge University Press, 2020.- 402 p.